

Multi-Stage Cascaded Algorithm for Localization with Integrated BEacon Ranking (CALIBER) for Bluetooth-Based Indoor Localization

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Abstract. Accurate indoor localization using Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) remains challenging due to high variability and noise in Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) measurements. This paper presents a multi-stage Cascaded Algorithm for Localization with Integrated BEacon Ranking (CALIBER) designed to enhance the accuracy of distance estimation and position inference in BLE-based systems. The proposed approach combines four successive processing stages: (1) beacon selection using a Minimum Composite Score criterion to filter unstable transmitters; (2) outlier removal through Median Absolute Deviation and Temporal Consistency Check; (3) residual noise reduction using Gaussian Kernel Smoothing; and (4) adaptive signal refinement via an Extended Kalman Filter. Filtered RSSI values are converted to distance estimates using a free-space path loss model, followed by trilateration to compute two-dimensional positions. Experimental evaluation in a corridor testbed demonstrates that the proposed CALIBER algorithm achieves a 56.9% improvement in localization accuracy compared to unfiltered RSSI input, reducing the mean localization error from 4.58 m to 1.97 m. Furthermore, by excluding extreme static points that exhibit uncharacteristic signal behavior, the mean error is further reduced to 1.12 m. The system requires only BLE beacons as infrastructure, making it easy to deploy and a low-cost solution for indoor localization in various built environments.

1. Introduction

Indoor localization is critical in domains such as smart infrastructure, healthcare, logistics, and emergency response. While GPS serves outdoor environments reliably, indoor settings introduce signal blockage, attenuation, and multipath effects that render it ineffective. BLE offers a practical alternative, with low cost, energy efficiency, and widespread device compatibility [1].

BLE systems often rely on RSSI for distance estimation due to its simplicity and ubiquity. However, RSSI is highly unstable indoors, where reflections, obstructions, and device orientation cause significant variability [2,3]. Multipath propagation, attenuation, and temporal interference result in inconsistent readings [4,5], while dynamic changes in transmission power or frequency further distort the RSSI-distance relationship [6,7].

Despite these challenges, many systems still rely on raw or lightly filtered RSSI, limiting performance in real-world conditions. This work proposes a lightweight, multi-stage RSSI filtering pipeline designed for real-time use. CALIBER combines beacon selection optimization, outlier removal by combining Median Absolute Deviation and Temporal Consistency Check, Gaussian kernel smoothing, and Extended Kalman Filtering. Filtered RSSI values are converted

into distances using a calibrated path-loss model and fused via geometric trilateration. We evaluate performance under different beacon densities and mounting heights and assess the impact of each filtering stage.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 3 presents the proposed CALIBER algorithm; Section 4 describes the experimental setup; Section 5 reports and analyzes results; and Section 6 concludes and outlines directions for future work

2. Background and Related Work

Indoor positioning systems face significant challenges due to the volatile nature of indoor environments, which causes substantial fluctuations and noise in RSSI. To overcome these issues and enhance positioning accuracy, various filtering and smoothing techniques are crucial for real-time preprocessing of RSSI measurements. These techniques stabilize fluctuating values, remove noise and outliers, and extract discriminative features, ultimately leading to improved localization performance.

Statistical filters such as mean, median, and moving average are widely used to suppress short-term RSSI fluctuations due to their simplicity and low computational cost, especially in proximity-based or geometric localization systems. Mean and median filters have been applied with logarithmic path-loss models to improve stability in short-range scenarios [8]. A maximal filter used in a sliding window context proved effective in reducing variance when integrated with particle-filter-based localization [9]. In larger-scale environments, moving average filters combined with fingerprinting and nearest neighbor matching achieved over 90% room-level classification accuracy [10], while weighted k-NN with averaging yielded approximately 1.4 m error in classroom settings [11]. Averaging was also used in evacuation scenarios, achieving 97% localization within 10 m [12], and combined with enhanced trilateration and pedestrian dead reckoning to reach 1.3 m error in dynamic settings [13].

Adaptive filters like Kalman and Extended Kalman Filters (EKF) are commonly used in geometric and tracking-based systems to smooth RSSI over time. Kalman filtering prior to trilateration enabled sub-decimeter accuracy in low-noise BLE 5.0 environments [14]. EKF has also improved the stability of machine learning classifiers in fingerprinting pipelines, reaching 96% classification accuracy [15]. In a multi-model fusion approach, Kalman filtering was combined with magnetometer calibration and low-pass filtering to reduce localization error to 0.72 m and achieve 99% orientation classification accuracy [16].

Outlier rejection plays a key role in RSSI preprocessing, particularly in fingerprinting. A combination of range limitation, 2-sigma rejection, and clustering (Natural Breaks Classification) was used to filter RSSI before applying AoA-enhanced fingerprinting with Random Forest-weighted k-NN, resulting in sub-0.5 m localization error [17].

Transform-based filtering methods use dimensionality reduction and spectral analysis to improve RSSI feature quality. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was used to compress RSSI data before fusing it with AoA information in a CNN-based pipeline, achieving 94.2% accuracy in an office environment [18]. Signal transformation techniques including FFT, Gray filters, and Wavelets have been evaluated, with Recursive Continuous Wavelet Transform (R-CWT) achieving 98.04% classification accuracy within a 1.5 m margin [19].

Machine learning-based filtering methods target non-linear noise patterns that traditional filters may miss. A Denoising Autoencoder (DAE) trained with adaptive noise generation schemes outperformed Kalman and Gaussian filtering, yielding 72.6% classification accuracy and 25.1 cm localization error in a fine-grained grid setup [20]. Although less common as standalone methods,

Gaussian filters have been used in offline radio map construction. Gaussian smoothing applied to corridor and hall environments yielded lower RMSE in narrow spaces (1.0–1.5 m) than in larger open areas (2.0–3.0 m), influenced by beacon layout and environmental structure [21].

3. The proposed CALIBER Algorithm

This section presents the proposed CALIBER for refining Bluetooth RSSI signals and estimating user position with improved accuracy. Indoor environments present significant challenges for BLE-based localization due to multipath propagation, where reflected signals from surfaces such as walls, floors, and nearby objects interfere with the direct line-of-sight signal. This phenomenon introduces erratic fluctuations and abrupt spikes in the RSSI measurements, even under static conditions, severely affecting the reliability of distance estimation and position tracking.

To address these issues, the proposed algorithm (Figure 1) incorporates a sequence of filtering and estimation stages, each tailored to mitigate a specific class of signal distortion. **PHASE#1:** Large anomalies caused by transient reflections are first suppressed through robust statistical outlier detection. **PHASE#2:** Residual small-scale noise is then attenuated using smoothing techniques, and **PHASE#3:** temporal inconsistencies are corrected through adaptive filtering. By progressively stabilizing the RSSI values prior to their conversion into distance and position estimates, the pipeline offers a resilient solution to the volatility induced by multipath effects and hardware-induced signal variation.

Figure 1: CALIBER - Indoor localization algorithmic pipeline

The complete pipeline consists of two main modules: an RSSI filtering pipeline and a post-filtering localization module.

Beacon Selection via Minimum Composite Score (MCS): Given the varying quality of signals from different beacons, the first step is to select those that offer the most stable and strongest RSSI values. A MCS is calculated using two metrics: the mean RSSI and its standard deviation (σ). First, each beacon's RSSI and standard deviation are normalized. Weights are assigned to each metric emphasizing on stability, as high variance in RSSI typically indicates unreliable signal behavior, which is more harmful to localization accuracy than moderate RSSI. The MCS is calculated per beacon and beacons are ranked by score, and the top subset is retained for processing

$$\text{minCompositeScore}_i = w_1 \times (1 - \text{MeanRSSI}_{\text{norm},i}) + w_2 \times \sigma_{\text{norm},i}$$

To improve the reliability of subsequent smoothing and localization steps, it is essential to first suppress extreme RSSI values that deviate significantly from the expected signal pattern. A two-pronged outlier removal approach is adopted, combining global statistical dispersion and local temporal coherence. Each method targets a distinct type of anomaly, and their joint application enhances robustness across diverse noise profiles.

Median Absolute Deviation (MAD): is a robust metric less sensitive to extreme values than standard deviation. For a given beacon's RSSI sequence $\{r_t\}$ the MAD is defined as:

$$MAD = \text{median}(|r_t - \tilde{r}|)$$

Where \tilde{r} is the median RSSI value. A sample is considered an outlier if:

$$|r_t - \tilde{r}| > k \times MAD$$

The threshold k is tuned empirically to reject large deviations while retaining natural variability in the signal.

Temporal Consistency Check (TCC): evaluates the local coherence of the signal. An RSSI value x_t is flagged as an outlier if it shows a sharp deviation from both its immediate neighbors:

$$|x_t - x_{t-1}| > T_c \quad \wedge \quad |x_t - x_{t+1}| > T_c$$

This local threshold T_c is designed to detect short-lived spikes or drops that are unlikely to reflect physical movement or environmental changes. Unlike MAD, which captures global outliers, this step is sensitive to abrupt transitions in time.

Samples failing either condition are marked as outliers and replaced with the local median to preserve temporal continuity. The combination of these two filters enables effective removal of both persistent anomalies and transient spikes, preparing the signal for finer-grained smoothing in the next stage.

Gaussian Kernel Smoothing (GKS): A kernel smoother is a method used to reduce noise in a signal by averaging nearby values, where closer points are given more weight than distant ones. It does not assume a fixed mathematical model for the data, but instead relies on the structure of the observed values. Among the various kernel types, the Gaussian kernel is widely used due to its smooth and symmetric shape, which emphasizes central values while gradually reducing the influence of those farther away. Given a cleaned RSSI sequence $\{r_t\}$, the smoothed value \hat{r}_t at time t is computed as a weighted average over a symmetric window of size $W = 2k + 1$, where k defines the number of points on either side of the center. The value r_{t+j} represents the RSSI sample at offset j and the associated Gaussian weight w_j is defined by the Gaussian function:

$$\hat{r}_t = \sum_{j=-k}^k w_j \times r_{t+j} \quad \text{where} \quad w_j = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} e^{-\frac{j^2}{2\sigma^2}}, \quad \sum_{j=-k}^k w_j = 1$$

The standard deviation σ controls the spread of the kernel, influencing how rapidly the weights decay with distance from the center. The weights are normalized to ensure that their sum equals one, preserving the scale of the signal.

This smoothing step is applied after the outlier removal stage (MAD and temporal consistency) to ensure that large discontinuities or non-representative spikes are not included in the weighted

average. Applying Gaussian smoothing directly to unfiltered data would risk blurring anomalies into valid signal regions, reducing both accuracy and interpretability. By first removing outliers, the kernel smoother operates over a more reliable signal, enhancing local stability without introducing bias

Extended Kalman Filter (EKF): To improve temporal consistency, the final stage applies an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) using the `ExtendedKalmanFilter` class from the `FilterPy` library. The EKF adaptively refines the RSSI estimate by combining previous values with new observations, accounting for their uncertainty. This reduces residual jitter and stabilizes the signal over time, which is critical for reliable distance estimation.

Distance Estimation via FSPL Model: Following the RSSI filtering stages, signal strength is converted into distance using the Free-Space Path Loss (FSPL) model. This empirical model relates RSSI values to the distance between the receiver and each beacon under ideal line-of-sight conditions. Let \hat{r}_i be the filtered RSSI value from beacon i , P_0 the reference RSSI at a distance of 1m, and n the path-loss exponent. The estimated distance d_i is given by:

$$d_i = 10^{\left(\frac{P_0 - \hat{r}_i}{10n}\right)}$$

To calibrate P_0 , the RSSI was measured at a fixed distance of 1 meter from each beacon, and the average value was used as the reference.

Position Estimation via Trilateration: Once distances are estimated from the filtered RSSI values, the receiver's 2D position is computed using trilateration. This technique estimates the position by finding the point that best fits the measured distances to at least three beacons with known coordinates.

Let x_i, y_i be the known position of beacon i and d_i the estimated distance from the receiver to beacon i . The receiver's position (\hat{x}, \hat{y}) is determined by minimizing the sum of squared differences between the actual and estimated distances

$$(\hat{x}, \hat{y}) = \underset{x,y}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\sqrt{(x - x_i)^2 + (y - y_i)^2} - d_i \right]^2$$

The final step in the localization pipeline estimates the 2D position of the receiver using geometric trilateration. This method requires at least three beacons with known coordinates and their respective distance estimates, previously derived from the filtered RSSI values. Given three selected beacons located at (x_1, y_1) , (x_2, y_2) and (x_3, y_3) and corresponding distances d_1, d_2, d_3 , the user's position (\hat{x}, \hat{y}) is determined by solving the system of equations:

$$(x - x_i)^2 + (y - y_i)^2 = d_i^2 \text{ for } i = 1, 2, 3$$

4. Experimental setup & configuration

To evaluate CALIBER algorithm, experiments were conducted in a controlled indoor environment designed for repeatable, high-resolution testing of BLE signal behavior under various configurations. The system consisted of BLE beacons (Blue Puck RHT) and a BLE gateway (Trax20203), which continuously scanned and logged RSSI values. Beacons were configured with a transmit power of 0 dBm and a broadcast interval of 200 ms, balancing energy efficiency with sufficient sampling density for robust filtering.

Three layouts (Figure 2) with varying number of beacons were tested to assess the effect of density and placement on localization accuracy: CFG_1 (4 beacons, 4.3 m spacing), CFG_2 (6 beacons, 2.6 m), and CFG_3 (7 beacons, 2.2 m). Beacons were evenly spaced along the 13 m corridor to ensure consistent coverage. Each layout was tested at two mounting heights, 1.2 m and 2.5 m, representing typical wall-mounted and near-ceiling scenarios. The receiving device was worn at chest level, suspended from the user’s neck.

The corridor was 0.7 m wide and 3 m high, with brick walls and no obstructions, simulating industrial environments like tunnels or mines. Fourteen static reference points were marked along the corridor at 1 m intervals. At each point, 30 s of RSSI data were recorded, yielding approximately 150 samples per beacon. For each configuration and height, data were collected independently, resulting in 16,800 samples (CFG_1), 25,200 samples (CFG_2), and 29,400 samples (CFG_3). This provided a comprehensive dataset for analyzing filtering performance and localization accuracy.

Figure 2: Spatial layout of the configurations used in the corridor-based experimental setup

5. Experimental Studies

This section presents a series of experiments designed to evaluate the performance and robustness of the proposed RSSI-based indoor localization pipeline. The study systematically analyzes the effect of individual filtering stages (Exp. #1), the effect of omitting individual filtering stages (Exp. #2), and key deployment parameters including beacon density (Exp. #3) and mounting height (Exp. #4).

Experiments 1 and 2 used configuration CFG_3 with a beacon height of 2.5 m. All experiments were conducted in the same indoor corridor using 14 static reference points.

Experimental Study #1 (Figure 3-left) quantifies the effect of different RSSI filtering strategies on localization accuracy. The full filtering pipeline is evaluated against a raw RSSI baseline and partial configurations that apply only one filtering stage, MAD & TCC, GKS, or EKF to assess each module’s contribution. The full pipeline reduced mean localization error from 4.58 m (baseline) to 1.97 m. The MAD + TCC configuration achieved the lowest error (1.91 m), slightly outperforming the full pipeline on this dataset. Gaussian smoothing (3.63 m) and EKF (3.35 m) also improved accuracy, though less significantly. While the full pipeline did not achieve the absolute lowest error, it combines multiple complementary filtering stages that are expected to offer improved robustness and generalization in more dynamic environments.

Experimental Study #2 (Figure 3-right) investigates the contribution of each filtering module within the full pipeline by systematically disabling one component at a time. The evaluation compares the full pipeline to three ablated versions—without MAD, without Gaussian smoothing, and without EKF, thereby isolating the impact of each stage. Removing the MAD filter significantly worsened performance, increasing the mean error from 1.97 m to 3.08 m and the standard deviation from 1.39 m to 4.93 m, confirming its critical role. Excluding Gaussian smoothing had no impact on mean error, while removing EKF and TCC slightly reduced it (1.93 m and 1.87 m, respectively)

Figure 3: Evaluation of full filtering pipeline against raw RSSI baseline and partial configurations (left) and evaluation of each filtering module contribution within the full pipeline by systematically disabling one component at a time (right)

Experimental Study #3 (Figure 4-left) explores the effect of beacon density and spatial arrangement on localization accuracy. Three beacon configurations, CFG_1 (4 beacons), CFG_2 (6 beacons), and CFG_3 (7 beacons) were evaluated using the full filtering pipeline, with a consistent beacon height of 2.5 m. CFG_3 achieved the lowest mean Euclidean error (1.97 m), while CFG_1 and CFG_2 yielded similar results (3.41 m and 3.45 m). The improvement from 6 to 7 beacons may reflect more favorable geometric coverage and reduced blind zones. These observations underscore the role of deployment geometry and environmental structure particularly in constrained spaces such as corridors and should not be generalized without considering specific layout and coverage conditions.

Experimental Study #4 (Figure 4-right) evaluates the influence of beacon mounting height on localization performance, this experiment compares two height settings: 1.2 m and 2.5 m. The same spatial configuration (CFG_3) was used in both cases, and the full filtering pipeline was applied. Mounting the beacons at 2.5 m reduced the mean localization error from 3.03m to 1.97m. While this suggests that higher placement may reduce signal obstruction and improve propagation paths, these results should be interpreted in the context of the test environment. The corridor had a ceiling height of 3m allowing sufficient clearance above the beacons to minimize

ceiling reflections. Although raising the beacon height introduces a vertical component to the actual signal path, localization in this experiment was computed on a 2D plane. The observed improvement in accuracy may be attributed to better signal propagation conditions, such as reduced body obstructions or multipath effects, but we do not explicitly model or evaluate 3D effects in this setup.

Figure 4: Evaluation of effect of beacon density with 4,6 and 7 beacons (left) and evaluation of beacons height at 1.2m and 2.5m (right)

6. Conclusions and Future Work

This study presented the CALIBER, a multi-stage RSSI filtering pipeline for improving Bluetooth-based indoor localization and validated its effectiveness through controlled experiments. The full pipeline reduced mean localization error by 56.9% compared to raw RSSI. Among its components, MAD filtering proved most critical: removing it increased the mean error from 1.97 m to 3.08 m and the standard deviation from 1.39 m to 4.93 m, confirming its importance for outlier suppression. While Gaussian smoothing and EKF offered moderate gains in isolation, their assumptions (e.g., temporal continuity or motion dynamics) did not align with the static nature of the tests.

Moreover, beacon density significantly influenced performance: the 7-beacon configuration (CFG_3) consistently outperformed sparser layouts, enhancing spatial resolution and reducing both mean and maximum errors. Mounting beacons at 2.5 m yielded better results than 1.2 m, likely due to reduced obstructions and improved alignment with receiver height, though multipath effects remain a limiting factor in indoor environments.

Finally, if extreme static points exhibiting uncharacteristic signal behavior are excluded, the mean error is further reduced to 1.12 m. Importantly, the system requires only BLE beacons as infrastructure, making it easy to deploy and cost-effective for various built environments such as offices, tunnels, or public facilities.

CALIBER supports sustainability by relying solely on BLE beacons, which are inherently low-power and widely available and minimize the need for additional infrastructure. Since BLE beacons operate for years on small batteries, the system reduces operational costs and environmental impact by lowering battery consumption and limiting electronic waste. The filtering pipeline itself consists of computationally simple operations which can be implemented

embedded. While current experiments were conducted on a local machine, the algorithm was intentionally designed with modular, low-complexity components, suggesting its potential suitability for energy-constrained platforms. This infrastructure-light and computation-efficient approach enables scalable indoor localization without the need for energy-intensive hardware or cloud-based processing

Future work will assess performance under dynamic conditions involving user mobility and expand testing to larger, more complex indoor spaces. Enhancing the pipeline with adaptive filtering and ensuring computational efficiency for embedded platforms will support practical deployment. Overall, the results demonstrate that combining structured filtering with thoughtful beacon deployment provides a scalable, accurate, and low-cost foundation for real-world indoor localization.

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